

TERPENOID. PART II THE SYNTHESIS OF *dl*-PULEGONE*

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Starting from 2-carbethoxy-5-methylcyclohexanone, *dl*-pulegone has been synthesised by taking advantage of Salmi's method of protecting the keto group.

Pulegone, a pleasant smelling camphoraceous oil, is found somewhat widely distributed in nature (Simonsen, "The Terpenes", Cambridge University Press, 1947, Vol. I, p. 371). On the basis of degradative studies, Semmler (*Ber.*, 1892, 26, 3519) suggested the structure (IIIb) for pulegone, which was later corroborated by Wallach (*Annalen*, 1896, 289, 337). The $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturation was confirmed by its ultraviolet absorption spectrum (Naves and Papazian, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1942, 25, 1023, 1046 and references cited therein).

Although Tiemann and Schmidt (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 913; 1897, 30, 22) obtained pulegone from citronellal by the action of acetic anhydride through isopulegol-acetate, isopulegol and isopulegone, no direct synthesis was reported till Bardhan and Bhattacharyya (*Chem. & Ind.*, 1951, 800; cf. Kuhn and Schinz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, 36, 161) claimed to have effected a synthesis of pulegone by cyclisation of citronellic acid chloride, followed by dehydrohalogenation of the intermediate chloro-ketone. This synthesis, though apparently simple, is not, however, above scrutiny, in as much as it admits of the alternative possibility of the formation of cycloheptane and / or cyclooctane ring, especially from the isopropenyl form of citronellic acid. Furthermore, these authors have not so far established the structural identity of their synthetic sample with natural pulegone either through their spectral study or mixed melting points of their derivatives.

We have now worked out a different but simple and unambiguous route which actually constitutes a total synthesis of *dl*-pulegone (IIIb). As pilot experiments, ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate was treated with ethyleneglycol in presence of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid under the condition prescribed by Salmi (*Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1803; cf. Surber and Schinz; *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 37, 1239) when 2-carbethoxy-cyclohexanone-1-dioxolane (Ia) was obtained in 71% yield. Grignard reaction on this ketal with methylmagnesium iodide afforded a 95% yield of (2-keto-2-dioxolane)-cyclohexyldimethyl carbinol (IIa) which, on decomposition with acid, followed by distillation of the intermediate keto-alcohol (not isolated) with a trace of iodine (cf. Stauffacher and Schinz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 37, 1239), furnished 2-isopropylidene-cyclohexanone (IIIa) in 85% yield. That the double bond in (IIIa) remained exocyclic was checked by its absorption maximum in the ultraviolet region at 2527μ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.66) which is in conformity with the Woodward rule (Fieser and Fieser, "Natural Products related to Phenanthrene", Reinhold, 1949, p. 192) for exo-double bonded $\alpha\beta\beta$ -trialkyl-substituted cyclic ketone.

*Since this paper was in the press, a similar synthetic approach to *dl*-pulegone has been reported by Black *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2971). Their observations are in overall agreement with ours (added in proofs).

Ethyl 5-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (Kotz and Hesse, *Annalen*, 1905, 342, 306) was therefore subjected to the above sequence of reactions when 2-carbethoxy-5-methylcyclohexanone-1-dioxolané (Ib), (2-keto-2-dioxolane)-cyclohexyldimethyl carbinol (IIb) and 2-isopropylidene-5-methylcyclohexanone (IIIb) were obtained in 58%, 95% and 75% yield respectively. The sample (IIIb) showed ultraviolet absorption maximum at $253m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.745) in agreement with the value ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{obs}}$: $253m\mu$; $\log \epsilon$, 3.84) recorded by Naves and Papazian (*loc. cit.*) for natural pulegone. Furthermore, these values are in conformity with the Woodward rule.

Both the ketones (IIIa and IIb) furnish deep red 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones which, though prepared under acidic condition, are assigned to have *exo* C=C double bond, because under the mild condition employed, the double bond should not migrate into the ring (*cf.* Frank and Berry, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2985). Again, the semicarbazone of (IIIb), prepared under mild condition, melts at $169-70^\circ$ and is therefore formulated as the true semicarbazone and not the carbamyl pyrazoline derivative which is reported to have *m. p.* $156-57^\circ$ (*vide* Simonsen, *loc. cit.*). Similarly, the derivative obtained from (IIIa) under similar condition was designated as the true semicarbazone.

* E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-Carbethoxycyclohexanone-1-dioxolane (Ia).—A mixture of ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (50 g.), ethyleneglycol (22 g.), dry benzene (200 c.c.) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (100 mg.) was refluxed in an oil-bath (120°) in a Dean and Stark apparatus till no more water separated. The reaction mixture was neutralised with

*The melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

a little sodium ethoxide and sufficient water was added, and then worked up in the usual way when 45 g. (71%) of the ketal (Ia) distilled over at 120°-124°/8 mm., η_D^{20} , 1.4685. (Found: C, 61.23; H, 8.42. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 61.66; H, 8.47 per cent).

(2-Keto-2-äioxolane)-cyclohexyldimethyl Carbinol (IIa).—Grignard reagent, prepared from magnesium (4.9 g.) and MeI (30 g.) in dry ether (150 c.c.), was added dropwise to the above ketal-ester (Ia: 21.4 g.) in dry ether (100 c.c.) in the cold. After standing overnight the reaction mixture was decomposed with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride and worked up in the usual manner when the carbinol (IIa: 19 g.) was obtained in 95% yield, b.p. 160-62°/20 mm., η_D^{20} , 1.4753. (Found: C, 65.68; H, 10.23. $C_{11}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 66.0; H, 10.0 per cent).

2-isoPropylidene-cyclohexanone (IIIa).—The above ketal-alcohol (IIa: 19 g.) was hydrolysed by heating with a solution of alcohol (25 c.c.), water (240 c.c.) and four drops of HCl (conc.) for 1 hour on the steam-bath. It was then diluted with water and extracted three times with ether. The residue, obtained after removal of the solvent from the combined extract, was distilled with a grain of iodine under 20 mm. pressure, when 11.2 g. (85%) of the unsaturated ketone (IIIa) came over at 120°-125°; η_D^{20} , 1.4919; UV-absorption: λ_{max}^{alc} , 252 m μ (log ϵ , 3.66). (Found: C, 78.03; H, 10.31. $C_9H_{14}O$ requires C, 78.21; H, 10.14 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, prepared by the sulphuric acid method in the cold, was crystallised from ethyl acetate as red flakes, m. p. 162-63°. (Found: N, 17.20. $C_{16}H_{18}O_4N_4$ requires N, 17.60 per cent).

The semicarbazone was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 184°. (Found: N, 21.70. $C_{10}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 21.52 per cent).

2-Carboethoxy-5-methylcyclohexanone-1-dioxolane (Ib).—A mixture of 2-carboethoxy-5-methylcyclohexanone (Kotz and Hesse, *loc. cit.*, 14 g.), ethyleneglycol (10 g.), dry benzene (150 c.c.) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (100 mg.) was treated in the same way as in the case of the preparation of (Ia); when 10 g. (58%) of the ketal (Ib) was obtained, b.p. 152-55°/8 mm., η_D^{20} , 1.4653. (Found: C, 62.71; H, 8.74. $C_{12}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 63.13; H, 8.77 per cent).

(2-Keto-2-äioxolane-4-methyl)-cyclohexyldimethyl Carbinol (IIb).—A solution of the above ketal-ester (IIb: 8.5 g.) in dry ether (50 c.c.) was treated with methylmagnesium iodide (prepared from 1.8 g. of Mg and 12 g. of MeI in 100 c.c. of dry ether) under the same condition as in the case of (Ia). On working up in the usual manner 9 g. (95%) of the desired product (IIb) came over at 132-35°/7 mm., η_D^{20} , 1.4642. (Found: C, 66.97; H, 10.42. $C_{12}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 67.25; H, 10.28 per cent).

5-Methyl-2-isopropylidene-cyclohexanone (IIIb).—The above ketal-alcohol (8.5 g.) was refluxed for an hour with a solution of alcohol (10 c.c.), water (100 c.c.) and two drops of HCl (conc.). After working up in the usual manner, the residue was distilled under reduced pressure with a crystal of iodine, when 4.5 g. (75%) of *dl*-pulegone (IIIb) was obtained, b.p. 101-103°/10 mm., η_D^{20} , 1.4845 (Simonsen, *loc. cit.*, records for *d*-pulegone, b.p. 84°/6 mm., η_D , 1.4846); λ_{max}^{alc} , 253 m μ (log ϵ , 3.745) (Naves and Papázian, *loc. cit.*, record for *d*-pulegone, λ_{max}^{alc} , 253 m μ ; log ϵ , 3.84). (Found: C, 78.67; H, 10.43. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{24}O$: C, 78.89; H, 10.59 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, prepared by the sulphuric acid method in the cold, was crystallised from ethyl acetate as bright red needles, m. p. 142° (Brady, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 756, reported m. p. 142° for *d*-pulegone derivative). (Found: N, 16.7. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{10}O_4N_4$: N, 16.86 per cent).

The semicarbazone was prepared in the usual manner without heating the reaction mixture. On crystallisation from alcohol it melted at 169-70° (Bayer and Henrich, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 653, reported m. p. 172° for the *d*-pulegone derivative). (Found: N, 20.02. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{10}N_2O$: N, 20.08 per cent).

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